

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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WORK PACKAGE NUMBER & NAME:

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Deliverable D5.5 “Project Workshop” provides an overview on the aims of the RECAP pilot workshops. It is structured as a step –by – step guide to assist in the initial design of the four (4) project events of launching the pilot phase, as well as to enable any other workshops that may take place.

The concept behind the organization of the workshops is to gather potential stakeholders/users of the platform, in order to exchange information and thoughts on the RECAP platform and its components. It will at the same time offer them the opportunity to test the RECAP platform. The workshop outcomes will in turn provide useful feedback on the user satisfaction of the RECAP product, increasing its chances for market uptake.

The aim of this report is to assist partners in the organization and implementation of regional workshops for launching the pilot phase (WP4) in the participating countries. The workshops will be carried out in each of the four pilots (Greece, UK, Spain, Lithuania). Their aim is to present the RECAP platform as it will be tested, along with the logistics of the pilots, in order to allow local pilot partners to better involve the pilot actors as well as get the interest from other national stakeholders.

Future plans include a final RECAP dissemination event that will be organised in connection to the final project meeting, ideally as a satellite to a larger event in the field of remote sensing, earth observation, ICT or CAP.

It should be noted that by organizing these local events for launching the pilots, dissemination and communication goals are also served. It is expected that promotional actions for the workshops, as well as the participants themselves, will maximize dissemination of the project. Subsequently, the RECAP product will increase in visibility at least at a local / regional level. The Network of Interest will also be enriched by adding new members in the core – user group.

The present deliverable will be submitted updated (version 2) in Month 30, including details on the workshops carried out and their evaluation results.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose of the deliverable

The deliverable 5.5 “Project Workshop” analyses the methodology decided upon preparing the workshops and relative instructions for carrying out a successful workshop, in line with its aims. Additionally, templates of various forms that may be useful for organizational or dissemination purposes are presented in the annex. The targeted metrics of the RECAP project is to successfully carry out four regional workshops in each pilot country (Greece, UK, Lithuania and Spain).

The actions planned, intent to succeed in maximum results by disseminating the project and its products, engaging and informing the main user group in the pilot phase and attracting possible new users. RECAP project concept and platform evaluation that will be carried out during the workshop using a structured questionnaire will act as tool to assist in the general aims of the project. Such an ad-hoc survey is expected to provide feedback in product planning and give room for corrective actions. Additionally, these events will enhance dissemination of the project overall.

Finally, future activities planned on workshops or events until M30 are presented, when the next deliverable is due.

2.2 The nature of the “Project Workshop” deliverables

This deliverable is structured as a “workshop guide” describing all necessary organization and dissemination actions for the successful launching of the pilot workshops. Guidelines are given on the preparation stage, the day of the event and relative retrospective actions. The next deliverable, D5.9 Project workshop (2), is due on Month 30 (October 2018) and will be the final version of the Project workshop deliverable presenting an evaluation of the workshops results. This final version will include details on dissemination actions, survey results, attendances etc.

3. RECAP WORKSHOP

3.1 Definition

A workshop is a usually brief intensive educational program for a relatively small group of people that focuses especially on techniques and skills in a particular field. It may be defined as a training class or seminar in which the participants work individually and/or in groups to deal with actual work related tasks to gain hands-on experience. The workshops that are the object of this deliverable will focus on presenting the RECAP platform to as it will be tested, along with the logistics of the pilots to user groups (i.e. farmers and agricultural consultants) in order to familiarize them to the product by using a mock up application.

The concept behind organizing these events is to gather potential stakeholders/users of the platform, in order to exchange information and thoughts on the RECAP platform and its components, but also offer them the opportunity to test the RECAP platform. Their outcomes will in turn provide useful feedback to RECAP product, increasing its chances for market success.

These regional workshops will succeed in presenting the RECAP platform, allowing local pilot partners to better involve the pilot actors, as well as provoke the interest of other national stakeholders.

“I hear and I forget. I see and I remember. I do and I understand.”

Confucius

3.2 Aims

WP5.5 attempts to establish an organizational tool to assist partners in the implementation of regional workshops for launching the pilot phase (WP4) by providing them with a workshop guide and template forms. Each pilot partner will carry out one workshop. Their main goal is to involve targeted user group (i.e. farmers and agri-consultants) in testing the platform. Additionally the RECAP workshops aim at raising the interest of other national stakeholders and in general to disseminate the project.

3.3 Planning the workshop Agenda

The workshop agenda (annex B) for the regional launching of pilots was drawn in accordance to the aim of the project and in cooperation with the project leader, pilot partners and partners responsible for the platform design. It was built based on the concept that it should be short in duration so as for the audience not to get tired but long enough to communicate project aims. It should also be interactive to encourage active involvement and better understanding from the participants and possible future end users. Additionally, in order to attract participants the workshop should include guest speaker/s that are of general acceptance so that the workshop will gain prestige and attract greater audience.

The workshop should include a general introduction on the main subject, an in depth analysis of the product and a session where the participants may raise questions and discuss their concerns and opinion on the product / the subject under examination.

For feedback on workshop ideas an extensive web search took place and previous experience of all partners in similar projects was exploited. Then, when planning the workshop Agenda, the following methodology was followed:

- **Identification of the main points** – a list of main points to discuss was created, and then it was broken down into a detailed description of what is needed to be communicated.
- **Discussions and activities** – group discussions and activities based on the main points of the workshop were also listed. Interaction amongst a group of participants is a great tool for learning used in workshops. Therefore, it is necessary to include enough opportunities for every workshop participant to contribute meaningfully in the activities.
- **Time management** – based on the main points already decided upon, the duration of the workshop was estimated and thus the time schedule was drawn. It was based on the principle that presentations should not be longer than 20 minutes in order to keep up the participants' attention. Time for breaks was also calculated as people are more focused on tasks when they have the chance to take short breaks.
- **Expert speakers** - the need to recruit external experts as guest speakers was identified. They can provide important information and practical experience to the project. Additionally they can attract their own audience ensuring in this manner the desired attendance.

Additionally, tools that will help in the evaluation of both the workshop and the product were investigated and resulted in the:

- a) *Attendees questionnaire on their satisfaction and /or suggestions on the RECAP product*
- b) *Workshop Inventory*
- c) *Registration list*

Beyond the audiovisual materials that will be used by the speakers and in order to support interactive participation of participants, a Mock up mobile application was suggested.

The reasoning behind workshops planning and further steps necessary for their successful implementation are described in the following chapters. They are presented as a workshop guide to be used both in the pilot workshops or any other events that may be organized in the future as the project progresses.

4. PREWORKSHOP ACTIVITIES

The organization of a successful workshop requires forethought and careful planning. It requires an experienced work team, effective dissemination actions, appropriate scheduling, strict time frames and solid coordination between organizers, participants and third parties.

The main pre-workshop activities that need to be addressed are outlined in the following:

PHASE 1 → Setting up the workshop team

Setting up an appropriate workshop team is of utmost importance in order to manage effective and timely organization of the tasks necessary. The best organizational scheme is set in two levels, so that roles and responsibilities are clear:

- **Lead Workshop Organizer**, who will be the person ultimately responsible for planning and organizing the workshop.
- **Workshop Organizers**, are the team members responsible to plan, coordinate, execute, and follow through on the workshop outcomes. Amongst the organizers team the following duties should be assigned to appropriate team members:
 - ☑ **IT Expert**, who is the person to provide advice or manage on audio, visual, remote broadcasting, and other technical considerations and will also run the audio/visual/technical aspects of the workshop.
 - ☑ **Project Assistants / Event Coordinators**, people responsible for coordinating hotel contracts, catering contracts and transportation to the venue; arrange travel plans for guest speakers and additionally coordinate other logistical aspects.
 - ☑ **Workshop Instructors / Facilitators Moderators**, staff or partners onsite at the event who give presentations content or provide assistance with various aspects.

PHASE 2 → Decide on the speakers and participants

Apart from the organization team, decisions need to be made on the selection of appropriate speakers, guest speakers and the type and number of participants.

Main Speakers should be carefully selected amongst pilot partners and third parties based on their involvement on the project, expertise and ability to interact with audience / participants.

Guest speakers should be selected amongst experts on the subjects of CAP or remote sensing, working in ministries or academia and make sure their profile is extrovert enough to attract participants.

Participants should be chosen amongst the possible user groups, whilst they might also be representatives from agricultural organizations or institutes. They may act as multipliers of the knowledge and results of the workshop. The desirable number of participants should also be decided on.

PHASE 3 → Create an event

Create the Event on RECAP webpage with known meeting details, including: date, time, RECAP page link, agenda, instructions, etc. This page should constantly be updated as more information on the workshop becomes available.

PHASE 4 → Registration and dissemination of the workshop

Regarding registration, an appropriate form (annexed) should be created using Google docs. Registrants' first name, last name, institution / occupation and contact information (telephone, email address) need to at least be collected.

A deadline should be set for registration and no exceptions are to be made.

Disseminate the workshop using RECAPs webpage, (or create a RECAP workshop webpage), social media and other sources like newspapers, mailing lists (from the established Network of Interest) and the partners' webpages and social media to inform the community of the workshop. Make sure details are included on the agenda, place and time and details on the target audience (see annex for invitation letter).

When the registration has been concluded and based on the data available, it needs to be decided on who is on the approved list. There may be registrants who do not qualify for the workshop. Then, follow up with the successful registrants that have been selected, to confirm their status, and give the contact information. This step is important in order to create a complete and accurate list. Keep updating the participant lists with last minute changes that may come up.

PHASE 5 → Arrange venue and apparatus

This phase covers the following:

Select a potential venue and ensure the venue has adequate space for the meeting and breakout groups.

Determine the **availability and cost** of hotels in the area to accommodate speakers, guest speakers and possible guests.

Determine **catering needs**.

Determine the best **means of transport** to the venue.

Consult with the IT Expert on audio, visual and other **technical considerations** for the workshop and coordinate regarding availability of equipment.

PHASE 6 → Hosting guest speakers

As far as the hosting is concerned, two steps are necessary:

Make sure **guest speakers** remain available as workshop planning is being finalized.

Arrange / assist in their **travel plans**.

PHASE 7 → Workshop Contents

Coordinate with workshop instructors to make sure they are in sync with the overall desired intent of the workshop.

Coordinate with workshop facilitators to make sure they know what their responsibilities are.

Make sure all **presentations are ready** on time by creating a dropbox account and setting a deadline for their delivery.

PHASE 8 → Final details

Plan for coffee and snack **breaks**.

Contact the hotel to discuss any last minute details. If possible, request early access to the meeting space so that IT Expert can setup and test audio/visual/technical equipment.

Create name tags.

Create an inventory on items that will be provided by the venue and items it is needed to bring along (see annex).

Make sure the total budget as presented in the workshop proposal is known.

5. WORKSHOP

On the day of the event additional tasks need to be carried out, where careful organization is of utmost importance. At this point all tasks need to be coordinated and executed as planned and described in the following. A useful tool, the workshop inventory, is presented in the annex to assist in listing all necessary details and the allocation of tasks.

PHASE 1 → Preparatory work

- ✓ **Allocate clear duties** within the facilitator team so that there is no overlapping and an even distribution of the team is succeeded in the area and provision of support.
- ✓ **Arrive early to have** plenty of time to set up the space and meet with technicians, caterers, or team members before the workshop begins.
- ✓ **Set up the registration table** and make sure all necessary items are available (i.e. registration lists, pens).
- ✓ **Set up all equipment before participants arrive**, including computers, laptops, projectors and speakers and make sure they are fine-tuned in advance.
- ✓ **Arrange the chairs in advance.**
- ✓ **Distribute materials**, including notebooks or other workshop materials to hand out and place them on the tables in advance.
- ✓ **Make special plans** for guest speakers (welcome committee, seat allocation, goodbye meal).

PHASE 2 → During the Event

- ✓ **Welcome participants as they arrive** and get to know them before the start of the workshop. This helps in building relationships with the participants. Workshop facilitators are present during participant check-in on workshop day to welcome attendees and handout name badges.
- ✓ Workshop organizers need to **work along** with the workshop instructors to provide logistics and support as necessary.
- ✓ **Take pictures and videos** of both the instructors and the participants. Make sure at least one picture is shot per session.
- ✓ **Disseminate** the event in social media – real time.
- ✓ Hand out the **evaluation questionnaire** at the end of the workshop.
- ✓ **Conclude the workshop with a summary of what they have learned.** One of the workshop instructors should be selected beforehand and informed that he /she is required to sum up the workshop at its closing.
- ✓ **Get feedback immediately after the session**, using the evaluation form designed (annexes) that participants can fill out in the last few minutes of the workshop, making sure that enough time is left to

comment and consider the questions asked carefully.

- Organise the shooting of a **group picture**, having previously selected the appropriate setting. The picture may be used later on in the press release.

**Make sure all presentations, leaflets, folders etc.
use the templates of RECAP dissemination pack.**

6. POST-WORKSHOP ACTIVITIES

Once the workshop is concluded there is still work to be carried out. A workshop is carried out to produce results that can be measured and exploited both for the improvement of the project and for communication / dissemination purposes. The tasks that need to be carried out following the workshop include the following:

- Update attendance list** with the workshop name and names of all participants. Names should be put into the list in alphabetic order and separated in groups including facilitators, participants and instructors.
- Prepare a **Press release** including photos (ie group photo).
- Evaluate the survey results**. Share with the team any interesting findings and/or items for improvement.
- Write a **workshop report** for posting on the website, social media or forward it to the Network of Interest mailing list.
- Update **RECAP workshop webpage** with links to the workshop presentations, summaries, photos, report, and evaluation.
- Disseminate the workshop survey** to promote the outcomes of the workshop.
- Arrange **financial issues – payments**.
- Follow up with the participants** a few days or weeks later. This might reveal new insights on the impact of the workshop and additionally help retain contact with potential users.

ANNEX A - Workshop planning “at a glance”

ANNEX B - Workshop agenda

DATE

Topic	Presenter	Time allotted
Registration		
SESSION 1.		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Welcome brief on the scope of the workshop		09:00-09:15
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The current and future CAP		09:15-09:35
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The system of controls of agricultural payments		09:35-09:55
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology; a catalyst between agriculture and the environment		09:55-10:15
Coffee break		10:15-10:35
SESSION 2.		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RECAP project presentation		10:35-10:55
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The RECAP platform		10:55-11:15
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Live demonstration		11:15-11:35
Coffee break		11:35-12:00
SESSION 3.		
Question & Answers – Groups Discussion		12:00
Summary		12:45

Tools:

- a) Attendees questionnaire on their satisfaction and /or suggestions on the RECAP product
- b) Mock up mobile application
- c) Registration list

ANNEX C - Attendees questionnaire on their satisfaction and /or suggestions on the RECAP product

QUESTIONNAIRE

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this product and workshop evaluation. Your comments will enable us to upgrade RECAP product and execute future seminars tailored to your needs.

Sincerely,
[MANAGER NAME]
[MANAGER TITLE]

PART A: WORKSHOP EVALUATION

How would you rate the workshop overall?

Excellent
 Good
 Neutral
 Poor
 Bad

Please rate the following aspects of the workshop presentations?

	Excellent	Good	Neutral	Poor	Terrible
Usefulness of information presented	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Quality of the presentations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Handouts provided during the seminar	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Was the presentation level too easy for you?

Much too easy
 Somewhat easy
 Just right
 Somewhat difficult
 Difficult

Please rate the following aspects of the seminar organization

	Excellent	Good	Neutral	Poor	Terrible
Scheduling and time length	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Choice of facility/venue	<input type="checkbox"/>				

PART B: PRODUCT EVALUATION

How satisfied are you by the RECAP tool demonstrated?

Extremely satisfied
 Very satisfied
 Neutral
 Very dissatisfied
 Extremely dissatisfied

Do you believe that the average farmer of your country is able to use a platform requiring computer and mobile use?

Yes
 Most likely
 Likely
 Unlikely
 No

Which of the following benefits is most useful to you?

Farmers

- Reduce administrative burden
- Integration of user-generated data
- Support to comply with regulations imposed by the CAP
- Personalised information for simplifying the interpretation of complex regulations
- Early alerts on potential breaches
- Advice and guidance invigoration

Consultants

- Improving the efficiency and transparency of the compliance monitoring procedure
- Support the economic, environmental and territorial objectives of CAP
- Significant reduction of time and resources required for field visits
- Extra data for classification procedures
- Potential to create add-ons to the main application
- Access data available in the platform

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According to you which of the given features should be improved?

.....

.....

.....

.....

Do you know of a related product-service to RECAP? If yes, name the provider and product?

Yes No

PART C: GENERAL INFORMATION

Gender: Male Female

Age group: Under 20 20-29 30-39 40-49 50-59 60+

Name:	:
Occupation	:
Email	:

Thank you for taking part in the survey

ANNEX E - Workshop inventory

VENUE	CONTACT PERSON	PROGRESS
No of chairs arranged as agreed (no of attendees + facilitators + speakers)		
Extra chairs		
Secretarial/Registration table		
Projector & Screen		
Flipchart & Marker		
Laser Pointer		
Speakers table		
Water and glasses for speakers		
Water and glasses for attendees		
Power plugs and sockets		
Coffee Break @ (10:15-10:35)		
Coffee Break @ (11:35-12:00)		

ORGANISATION	PERSON RESPONSIBLE	PROGRESS
Badges		
Participants' List		
Banner		
RECAP Notepads / pens		
Folders /pens		
Workshop Agenda		
Questionnaires		
Backdrop Slide		
Camera		
Digital Recorder		
Laser Pointer		
Laptop		
Speakers ppt's		
Wi-Fi Access Sign		
Personal Business Cards		
Group Photo		

ANNEX F - Invitation Letter

PERSONALISED PUBLIC SERVICES IN SUPPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CAP

RECAP

Reinforcing CAP

Let's practice on CAP!

When? Where?

RECAP offers a unique workshop to discuss and demonstrate an improved monitoring of the CAP obligations through remote sensing and modern ICT. The idea is to combine state-of-the-art remote sensing with modern ICT and get a service tool for all stakeholders involved in cross-compliance implementation and monitoring (farmers, agricultural consultants, paying agencies). RECAP aspires to offer farmers the ability to comply with regulations, enable agricultural consultants to develop their own services within the platform and reduce the administrative burdens for the Paying Agencies.

We welcome you to a project presentation where a live demonstration of RECAP platform will take place.

Become a part of the project and help us reinforce CAP

Who can join the workshop?

...

REGISTER NOW

We welcome farmers and their organizations, agricultural advisory services and consultants, agronomists, ICT and remote sensing, local and national authorities, ICT companies, remote sensing downstream companies...

Registration	
SESSION 1.	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Welcome brief on the scope of the workshop	09:00-09:15
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The current and future CAP	09:15-09:35
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The system of controls of agricultural payments	09:35-09:55
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology; a catalyst between agriculture and the environment	09:55-10:15
Coffee break	
	10:15-10:35
SESSION 2.	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> RECAP project presentation	10:35-10:55
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The RECAP platform	10:55-11:15
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Live demonstration	11:15-11:35
Coffee break	
	11:35-12:00
SESSION 3.	
Questions & Answers – Groups Discussion	12:00
Summary	12:45

«RECAP H2020 Project»

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ANNEX G - Google Docs Registration Form

RECAP Workshop

Time:
Venue:

*Required

REGISTRATION FORM

RECAP
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First Name *
Your answer

Last Name *
Your answer

Organisation/Company *
Your answer

Position *
Your answer

City *
Your answer

Country *
Your answer

Email *
Your answer

SUBMIT